

4Q70 (4QJer^a) frag. 14 + PAM 43.696 frag. 8 (Jer 11:5)

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For the official edition of the Dead Sea Scrolls Qumran Cave 4 Jeremiah manuscript 4Q70 (4QJeremiah^a or 4QJer^a) see Tov (1997), and for subsequent identifications of 4Q70 fragments see Tigchelaar (2020). For the edition and image of PAM 43.696 see Pike and Skinner (2001), who, however, do not comment anything on frag. 8.

The hitherto unidentified Qumran Cave 4 fragment, PAM 43.696 frag. 8 (see figure 1 next page), can be identified as originating from 4Q70, and can be joined to the bottom of 4Q70 frag. 14 (see join in figure 2 next page). It preserves the five letters **בַּת הַלֵּב** from Jer 11:5 and the very top of some letters of Jer 11:6. In the Tov edition, this fragment is placed in Col. VI, part 1 (Jer 11:3-6) (1997: 159).

References:

Pike, Dana M., and Andrew C. Skinner. *Qumran Cave 4 XXIII Unidentified Fragments, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33* (Oxford: Clarendon, 1997), 261-67, pl. XXXV.

Tigchelaar, Eibert. "Identification and Reidentification of Some Fragments of 4Q70 (4QJer^a)."
Textus 29 (2020): 193-200; <https://doi.org/10.1163/2589255X-02901006>

Tov, Emanuel. "70. 4QJer^a." In *Qumran Cave 4 X The Prophets, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 15* (Oxford: Clarendon, 1997), 145-70, pls. XXIV-XXIX.

Images of fragments taken from:

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285121>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284664>

Figure 1: PAM 43.696 frag. 8

Figure 2: 4Q70 frag. 14 + PAM 43.696 frag. 8